

Abstract:

Oxygen supply into the eastern South Pacific (ESP) oxygen minimum zone (OMZ) is investigated with the help of climatological Argo and dissolved oxygen data. Annual mean oxygen fluxes due to epineutral advection, epineutral turbulent diffusion and dianeutral turbulent diffusion are computed for the whole ESP and their relevance is assessed. Two main advective routes for oxygen supply are found: the traditional eastward equatorial/tropical pathway and a previously unaccounted (meridional) subtropical pathway. The subtropical pathway represents 45% of the advective oxygen supply at the core of the ESP OMZ (26.81 kg m^{-3}) and provides more net oxygen gain (8.8 kmol s^{-1}) than the equatorial/tropical pathway (3.6 kmol s^{-1}) at this neutral surface layer. This finding challenges the common assumption that all the (advective) meridional supply of subtropical waters into the ESP OMZ is deflected westward by a potential vorticity barrier. Instead, we find that this barrier blocks the equatorward flow only for layers deeper than 27.0 kg m^{-3} ; for shallower layers, this barrier stands closer to the Equator, enabling advective supply of oxygen from the subtropical gyre and eastern boundary current into the ESP OMZ. The oxygen fluxes are integrated for the entire volume of the ESP OMZ and the annual mean oxygen budget is revealed.

Fig. 1 (a) Map of the study area with the ESP OMZ delimited by the contour of $60 \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$ (white dashed line) and its core delimited by the contour of $19.5 \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$ (green dashed line). The background shows the climatological mean of dissolved oxygen ($\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$) from WOA-13 at the neutral surface of the ESP OMZ core ($\gamma_n = 26.81 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, $\sim 350 \text{ m}$). (b) Vertical section of the climatological mean of dissolved oxygen ($\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$) from WOA-13 at 7.5°S . Neutral density contours are included for reference (black dashed lines). This section is shown with a red dashed line in 1a.

Fig. 2 Potential vorticity contours ($\times 10^{-7} \text{ m}^1 \text{ s}^{-1}$) computed for the isoneutral layer centred at (a) $\gamma_n = 26.18 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ and (b) $\gamma_n = 26.81 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$. The background colour shows the thickness (m) of the isoneutral layer. The ESP OMZ boundary is represented by a single red dashed line. Potential vorticity is calculated as f/H , where f is the Coriolis parameter and H represents the thickness of the isoneutral layer. The relative vorticity is neglected as it is assumed to be much smaller than the planetary vorticity.

Fig. 3 (a) Colour-coded geostrophic velocity vectors (cm s^{-1}) and geopotential anomaly contours ($\text{m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$) at the core of the ESP OMZ ($\gamma_n = 26.81 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, $\sim 350 \text{ m}$). The OMZ boundary (contour of $60 \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$) is shown with a single red dashed line. (b) Distribution of the advective oxygen fluxes at the core layer of the ESP. The OMZ boundary and its core (contour of $19.5 \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$) are shown with white dashed lines. (c) Meridional advective oxygen fluxes across a zonal section at 27°S (positive northward). The Peru-Chile Current (PCC), the Poleward Undercurrent (PUC), the subtropical gyre meridional flow (STG), the Southern Subsurface Countercurrent (SSCC), the South Equatorial Countercurrent (SECC) and relevant neutral surfaces (blue dotted lines) are shown. Oxygen flux units: $\mu\text{mol s}^{-1} \text{ m}^2$. The location of this zonal section is shown in 3b (black line).

Fig. 4 (a) Advective oxygen supply into the ESP OMZ (across the isosurface of $60 \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$) for each individual pathway per isoneutral layer (comparison between supply and net gain). (b) Net oxygen transports into the ESP OMZ due to epineutral advection, epineutral turbulent diffusion and dianeutral turbulent diffusion per isoneutral layer. (c) Terms involved in the annual mean oxygen budget of the ESP OMZ. All data shown is in kmol s^{-1} . Thin lines represent the 95% confidence interval for each term after an error propagation analysis.

Conclusions

✓ Our results indicate a significant subtropical (advective) supply of oxygen into the ESP OMZ for $\gamma_n < 27.0 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, in contrast with the previous view that advective ventilation can only occur via the eastward currents in the Equatorial Current System (Czeschel *et al.*, 2011; Stramma *et al.*, 2010) due to a potential vorticity barrier (Luyten *et al.*, 1983).

✓ This subtropical supply is possible because of the equatorward displacement of the potential vorticity barrier in these relatively shallower isoneutral layers.

✓ The subtropical advective supply leaks from the north-westward flow of the subtropical gyre and from the equatorward eastern boundary current (Humboldt or Peru-Chile Current) and represents around 45% of the total (equatorial + subtropical) advective oxygen supply at the core of the ESP OMZ (26.8 kg m^{-3} , $\sim 350 \text{ m}$), providing considerably more net oxygen gain (8.8 kmol s^{-1} , 12%) than the equatorial pathway (3.6 kmol s^{-1} , 5%) in the core layer of the ESP OMZ.

✓ Regarding the advective subtropical supply of oxygen (45% of the total advective supply): the Humboldt Current is responsible for 53% and the remainder is supplied by the north-eastern limb of the subtropical gyre (47%).

✓ The complete annual mean oxygen budget for the ESP OMZ is calculated. The net oxygen supply is as follows: epineutral turbulent diffusion $417.4 \pm 43.0 \text{ kmol s}^{-1}$ ($2.15 \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$; 53%); epineutral advection, $292.7 \pm 25.2 \text{ kmol s}^{-1}$ ($1.49 \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$; 37%); dianeutral turbulent diffusion, $85.8 \pm 17.6 \text{ kmol s}^{-1}$ ($0.43 \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$; 10%). Assuming steady state, the mean biological consumption of oxygen required to close the budget is $795.9 \pm 195.0 \text{ kmol s}^{-1}$ ($4.07 \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$); this consumption estimate agrees remarkably well with previous independent estimates (Karstensen *et al.*, 2008).

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